

**ANALISIS POTENSI DAN STRATEGI PENGEMBANGAN OBJEK
WISATA AIR PANAS GAMPONG TERUJAK KECAMATAN
SERBAJADI KABUPATEN ACEH TIMUR**

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to obtain data regarding supporting factors as well as obstacles in the development of tourism object of Terujak Village Hot Spring, and to analyse possible strategies that can be implemented by the local community in developing the tourism object of Terujak Village Hot Spring, and to increase tourists visits. The research was located at tourism object of Terujak Village Hot Spring, Serbajadi Sub-District of Aceh Timur Regency. The research was conducted for two months from January until February of 2019. Method used for the data analysis is descriptive with qualitative approach, and SWOT analysis is used to obtain development strategy. The results of the analysis using matrix IFAS-EFAS demonstrates that the number of strengths and threats achieved the smallest number (-0,82) resulting in ST as the selected strategy. Based on SWOT diagram, strategy in quadran II which is ST strategy is a strategy that utilize strength factor to overcome thread factor.

Keywords: *Potential, Strategy, Tourism Object, Terujak Village Hot Spring.*